
The Use of Multimedia Tools in the Organization of Practical Classes in Information Technology in Higher Educational Institutions

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Annotation: The presented article describes the state, experience and prospects for the application of IT-technologies and multimedia tools in the educational process all universities. The features of the definitions of educational technologies and their constructive analysis. Introduced international experience in the use of multimedia educational and IT technologies in leading universities in the world. Shows some aspects of the application of IT- technologies at Pacific State University.

Keywords: IT-technologies, education, multimedia tools, methods of presentation of multimedia educational resources.

Educational technologies are quite diverse. Consider the most general definitions for this concept: Educational technologies can be considered either as the design of science or as a collection of various scientific interests directed towards for solving fundamental issues of teaching and social organization tions. From a practical point of view, educational technologies are defined as conditions vie formation of a certain level of knowledge, skills, which corresponds to a certain level of specialist competence. However, there are several Values pointed out by most researchers and practitioners [1]: The use of technology is fundamental: technology means systematic application of scientific knowledge to solve practical problems. It is a systematic, iterative process of promoting learning and performance by creating, using and managing appropriate, technologically supported processes and resources in the field of education [2]. Educational technologies are built on an integrated approach, which takes into account complexity and versatility of processes. Educational technologies (information technologies) in accordance with requirements of the International Association for Technical Education are used as a tool to improve the effectiveness of the educational process and learning. The use of multimedia technologies or audiovisual means as as a tool to improve the effectiveness of the learning process and the study of recommended by the International Association for Technology Education. This recommendation the recommendation is justified by the prospect of technical and technological development of management of various fields and the general educational level of application of information technologies in everyday life of society. At the same time, the area of education is concentrated chena on the development and use of theoretical foundations and the application of practical situations that allow you to effectively build learning processes. It can be noted that technology is both a tool and a catalyst. Congestion and can become the means by which changes in compliance with the needs of the present. It is also necessary to add that in order to realize the educational potential with the use of multimedia, from a qualified teaching staff needs not only support for the use of existing existing multimedia teaching aids, but also the formation of students' skills for independent creation and adaptation of such means.

World experience in the use of multimedia educational and IT technologies in leading universities. An analysis of global trends shows that the period of information tization of society in all developed countries naturally led to the formulation of the high requirements for the education system and for the very principles of organization tions of the process of translation of cultural and historical experience to the younger generation [4]. The emergence in the culture of a new intellectual educational and cognitive means with non- limited scope of application almost universally revealed the inadequacy existing traditional forms of education, its goals, content and ways of organizing lowerization.[4] We can agree with these theses. I just want to point out that introduction of information technologies into educational and scientific processes are not it is necessary to completely abandon the "old", but rational and proven education methods. It is necessary to organically integrate information technologies into existing processes, which will improve their efficiency: reduce or eliminate in general, the time spent on the mechanical reproduction of lecture material, you frees up time for the teacher to present practical examples, expand scale of information search and the like. It is necessary to restructure processes, combine different types of information technologies and methods of their application in away from educational goals, or by completely replacing inefficient processes new.

The use of multimedia technologies provides not only new opportunities opportunities in the organization of the educational process, but also participates in the development of creative properties of university students. But in order for the processes of active and interactive effective teaching methods have been effectively implemented, it is necessary to provide com- computer and multimedia equipment of the audience, to create information opportunities on access to external sources of information, develop appropriate multimedia courses with guidelines or rules (regulations- mi) use. Under such conditions, not only students, but also professorial the teaching staff acquire the relevant skills that are in demand in the educational and work environment, i.e. the quality of education is improving as a the basic system of development of society as a whole. And I would also like to note that multimedia ny technologies is one of the most rapidly developing areas of new in-formational technologies in the educational process.

Multimedia products provide tools and technology based on ve constructivist educational learning environment where students have the opportunity to ability to be included not only in the information field of lecture courses, but also in visual but to perceive modern technologies of education. There is an opportunity for personal participation of each student in independent research; conditions are formed for cooperation and active participation.

Another significant positive factor is the extensive information a field in which various methods and models of software simulation are possible roving. Educational materials presented in multimedia products include animated graphics, video and audio recordings that are integrated into the structured tailored to the specific tasks of the discipline or course, which contributes to learning and the acquisition of new knowledge is much more effective. Interactive nature of multi- media provides a space to enhance traditional "write and speak" methods teaching methods, allows more flexibility for students to adapt to indi- vidual visual learning strategy. It can be noted that the teacher use multimedia product frees up lecture time and it can provide students new information or the possibilities of multimedia products (for example, measures, give real examples of the use of certain strategic decisions ny in specific situations in the first case; build a graph step by step with comments physical materials in the second, etc.). For students, the use of modern lectures is also attractive: before the lesson, they can get acquainted not only with the text- mi lecture courses, but also to consider the entire course, which may allow you to build a lo- logical vision of the discipline as a whole, saves time on lecture notes, time is freed up for questions that can and should arise during the lesson. ty.

In conclusion, we can say that the use of computer technology allows you to create high-quality video recordings of lecture demonstrations, computer laboratory work and workshops, simulation animation models of physical phenomena and processes necessary to understand their essence. Moreover, modern computer facilities allow you to create simulators, models and conduct practical work that is not feasible in real conditions. It is especially important to change in cases where a direct experiment cannot be carried out. An example is can serve as a demonstration using a computer of genetic modeling of the company development tags, etc. It is important to note that the use of joint IT- technologies and classical teaching methods allows you to better build educational process, increase the efficiency of mastering specialized and gain additional skills in working with modern technical media properties.

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